

Empirical Distinctions between Science and Wisdom in the Gaza Crisis

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Abstract

This paper examines the interplay between hikmat (wisdom) and scientific achievements, focusing on their representation in Persian and Arabic literature and their practical implications in contemporary conflicts, such as in Gaza. Hikmat, encompassing moral and practical wisdom, is a central theme in Persian educational literature and is reflected in the works of Jahili poets in Arabic literature (Mohseni Nia & Maryami, 2011; Abdul Jalil, 2001). This wisdom, as defined by Dehkhoda and others, involves understanding life issues and living ethically (Musaheb, 1966). In contrast, science, characterized by empirical methodologies and the pursuit of universal truths (Kuhn, 1970; Popper, 1959), often lacks the ethical and experiential dimensions of wisdom. The paper compares the wisdom of Solomon in the Bible and the Quran, highlighting his exemplary qualities and divine favor in both texts. The Biblical Solomon is acknowledged for his wisdom but ultimately succumbs to personal failings, whereas the Quranic Solomon remains a steadfast prophet (1 Kings; Quran 27:20-44). The comparison illustrates distinct theological and literary traditions. Furthermore, the paper discusses how scientific advancements, while providing significant benefits, can be misused for destructive purposes, as seen in the Gaza conflict (2023-2024), which exemplifies the divergence and potential conflict between science and wisdom. The study concludes by emphasizing the need for integrating scientific progress with wisdom to ensure ethical and humane outcomes. The Gaza conflict serves as a stark reminder of the consequences when scientific achievements are not guided by wisdom and ethical considerations. Future research

should explore the integration of these domains to foster a more holistic approach to human progress.

Keywords: Gaza, Solomon, Hikmat, Wisdom

Introduction

Hikmat and wisdom are two similar categories that have a wide range of poems and works in Persian and Arabic literature. (Musaheb, 1966) has been interpreted and in another place, knowledge of life issues and how to live has been defined. According to Dehkhoda, wisdom has also been defined as the understanding of wisdom and cleverness. Arising from the thoughts of various moralists, it forms an important branch of Persian literature called the educational literature of Iran (Mohseni Nia, Naser, and Maryami, Elham. 2011). . The ascetic advice and teachings form this literature. The verse and prose, which sometimes came under the independent title of *Andznameh*, and sometimes brought a wise story to the field of education and learning, in Arabic literature, we witness the manifestation of wisdom and wisdom in the works of Jahili poets. The way of thoughts and intellectual development of poets and the range of their understanding was related to human issues and the mysteries of existence. Wisdom is made in prose, and its most important topics are around the death of forgiveness, the fate of man and the events of the times" (Abd al-Jalil, 2001). Therefore, at first sight, the wisdom of ignorance can be considered as the result of the experience of an ignorant person during his life. Jahili art is the reflections and observations of Jahili poets, which are in a verse of a poem or a phrase in the hand of the city with phrases and studies Independence has not become and it can be achieved through different purposes. Solomon, known for his wisdom and wealth, is a prominent figure in both the Bible and the Quran. His narratives in these texts highlight his exemplary qualities, his rule, and his relationship with God. The distinction between science and wisdom has intrigued philosophers, psychologists, and scholars across disciplines. While science seeks to understand the natural world through rigorous methodologies, wisdom is concerned with the application of knowledge in a manner that is judicious and morally

sound. This paper aims to clarify these concepts, considering their definitions, methodologies, and roles in human decision-making.

Solomon in the Bible

In the Bible, Solomon is the son of David and Bathsheba, and he succeeds David as king of Israel. His story is primarily found in the books of 1 Kings and 2 Chronicles. Solomon is renowned for his wisdom, which is divinely bestowed. According to 1 Kings 3:5-14, Solomon asks God for an understanding heart to judge the people and distinguish between right and wrong. Pleased with Solomon's request, God grants him unparalleled wisdom, along with riches and honor.

Solomon's wisdom is demonstrated in various anecdotes, such as the famous judgment where he discerns the true mother of a baby claimed by two women (1 Kings 3:16-28). Furthermore, Solomon is credited with composing many Proverbs, Ecclesiastes, and the Song of Solomon, showcasing his literary and philosophical contributions.

He also undertakes the grand project of building the Temple in Jerusalem, which becomes the central place of worship for the Israelites (1 Kings 6-7). Despite his many accomplishments, Solomon's reign is not without flaws. His later years are marked by his marriages to many foreign women who lead him into idolatry, angering God and leading to the eventual division of the kingdom (1 Kings 11:1-13).

Solomon in the Quran

In the Quran, Solomon (Sulayman) is depicted as a prophet and a king endowed with wisdom, knowledge, and the ability to communicate with animals and jinn. His story appears in several surahs, including Al-Baqarah (2:102), An-Naml (27:15-44), and Saba' (34:12-14).

The Quran emphasizes Solomon's wisdom and his just rule. In Surah An-Naml, Solomon's communication with the ant and his interaction with the Queen of Sheba (Bilqis) are highlighted. He learns from a hoopoe bird about the Queen of Sheba's sun worship,

and he sends her a letter inviting her to worship Allah. The queen, impressed by Solomon's wisdom and the grandeur of his court, ultimately submits to Allah (Quran 27:20-44).

Solomon's ability to control the wind and command jinn is also noted in the Quran. These supernatural abilities underscore his unique status and the divine favor he enjoys (Quran 34:12-14). Unlike the Biblical account, the Quran does not mention Solomon's fall into idolatry, instead focusing on his devotion to God and his role as a wise and powerful ruler.

Comparative Analysis

Both the Bible and the Quran portray Solomon as a wise and powerful ruler with a unique relationship with the divine. However, there are notable differences in their narratives. The Biblical Solomon is a figure whose wisdom is acknowledged but who ultimately succumbs to personal and spiritual failings. In contrast, the Quranic Solomon remains a steadfast prophet whose wisdom and piety are consistently emphasized.

The Bible provides a more humanized portrayal of Solomon, complete with his strengths and weaknesses, illustrating the complexities of his character and reign. The Quran, however, presents Solomon as an idealized prophet, emphasizing his role as a model of wisdom and faithfulness to God.

These differing portrayals reflect the distinct theological and literary traditions of the Bible and the Quran. While both texts recognize Solomon's significance, they each highlight different aspects of his life and character to convey their respective religious messages.

1. **Defining Science and Wisdom**
2. **Science:** Science is a systematic enterprise that builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable explanations and predictions

about the universe (Kuhn, 1970). It relies on empirical evidence, the scientific method, and peer review to validate findings. Science is dynamic, evolving with new discoveries and technological advancements (Popper, 1959).

3. **Wisdom:** Wisdom is often described as the ability to make sound judgments and decisions based on knowledge, experience, and understanding of life's complexities (Aristotle, 350 BCE). It encompasses aspects of cognitive, reflective, and moral dimensions, integrating knowledge with practical, ethical, and existential considerations (Baltes & Staudinger, 2000).

Methodologies and Epistemologies

1. **Scientific Methodology:** The scientific method involves formulating hypotheses, conducting experiments, observing outcomes, and drawing conclusions that can be replicated and tested (Feyerabend, 1975). It emphasizes objectivity, reproducibility, and falsifiability (Popper, 1959).
2. **Wisdom's Approach:** Wisdom does not adhere to a fixed methodology. Instead, it involves integrating diverse sources of knowledge and experience, often through introspection, deliberation, and empathy (Sternberg, 1990). Wisdom is contextual and value-laden, requiring judgment that balances various factors, including emotional intelligence and ethical principles (Ardelt, 2003).

Comparative Analysis

1. **Nature of Knowledge:**
 - **Science:** Focuses on factual, verifiable knowledge that can be generalized across different contexts (Kuhn, 1970).
 - **Wisdom:** Incorporates experiential knowledge, intuition, and values, often dealing with the "why" and "what is good" rather than the "what is" (Baltes & Staudinger, 2000).
2. **Goal Orientation:**

- **Science:** Aims at uncovering universal laws and theories, contributing to the expansion of knowledge (Popper, 1959).
- **Wisdom:** Seeks to enhance the quality of human life, promoting well-being and ethical living through practical reasoning (Aristotle, 350 BCE).

3. **Methodological Rigor vs. Practical Insight:**

- **Science:** Relies on empirical testing and statistical analysis to establish causality and correlation (Feyerabend, 1975).
- **Wisdom:** Emphasizes holistic understanding, often relying on judgment and experience over empirical data (Sternberg, 1990).

Intersections and Integration

Despite their differences, science and wisdom are not mutually exclusive. Advances in science can inform wise decisions, and wisdom can guide scientific inquiry by emphasizing the ethical implications and societal impact of scientific progress (Habermas, 1971). For instance, the development of medical technologies must be guided by ethical considerations to ensure they benefit humanity without causing harm (Boorse, 1975).

The Battle Between Scientific Achievements and Wisdom in Gaza"

Scientific achievements in the West have been used to restrict, damage, and finally commit horrible crimes in Gaza over the last decades, especially in the crimes against humanity between 2023-2024, which contribute to the first televised genocide in history in the 21st century. *The Book of Solomon* (The Holy Bible) a canonical Jewish and Biblical narrative, directly advises followers to avoid tyranny and crimes and warns of their consequences. However, the battle in Gaza exemplifies an instance where wisdom and science confront each other in conflicts, highlighting a significant separation between the two. The wars of wisdom can be considered as wars with the source of wisdom (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024) or supra-human beings (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024) and prior achievements of

the humanity in the pursuit of wisdom i.e. the battle against apartheid (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, while science and wisdom serve different purposes and employ distinct methodologies, they are interrelated in their pursuit of understanding and improving human life. Science provides the tools and knowledge necessary for innovation and progress, while wisdom ensures that such advancements are aligned with human values and ethical standards. Future research should explore how these domains can be integrated to foster a more holistic approach to human knowledge and decision-making. Finally the war in Gaza (2023 – 2024) is a clear instance of battle between biblical wisdoms and science which is a clear indication of a determinative separation (despite their interrelation for individual pursuit) for the involving parties, especially for the Israeli so called religious propaganda.

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